

PRODUCTION PLANNING CONSIDERING CAPACITY FLEXIBILITY AND BACKLOGGING

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ABSTRACT: In this work we address the production planning problem, precisely the lot sizing problem with parallel machines, product setups and considering backordering and overtime as capacity flexibility. The objective in this study is to establish an optimal production plan for a production unit composed of m non-identical parallel machines that perform the same operations to manufacture n type-products over t periods at a regular mode. When the demand of a product exceeds the production capacity, it can be manufactured at overtime or it have to be backlogged generating a backlogging cost. To solve the problem, we propose a mixed integer linear program (MILP) and a Simulated Annealing (SA) algorithm where the objective function (F) consists on minimizing the total cost that includes: production costs, inventory holding costs, setup costs, backlogging cost, overtime setup costs and overtime production costs.

KEYWORDS: backlogging, capacity flexibility, lot sizing, overtime, production planning.

1 INTRODUCTION

Production planning and capacity management continue to be of major importance for industrial companies, running in parallel at the tactical planning level. They enable companies to cope with fluctuating demand, while ensuring the right trade-off between inventory, set-up and production costs. The problem of production planning has been of interest to many researchers and manufacturers over the last decades, and in many different fields: (Garre and al., 2020), (Tahraoui, N and al 2024) in the food industry. (Walton and Metters, 2008) in the escape and rescue stair industry, (Djama and Sari, 2020) and (Djama and Sari, 2022) in thermoplastic tube industry, (Gupta, and Magnusson, 2005) in paper production, (Djama and Sari, 2023) in textile industry and y Smith-Daniels and(Benfriha, A and al 2024) in process industries.

One of the most studied production planning problems is the lot sizing problem for which many extensions have been added to the literature. (Karimi and al, 2003), (Jans and Degraeve, 2008), (Fellahi, H and al 2022) have realized literature reviews for the lot sizing problem including models and extensions

related to parallel machines, production capacity, backorders, setup carryover, setup crossover and sequencing. Flexibility in production capacity is defined by (Alp and Tan, 2008) as the use of contingent resources in addition to permanent resources to increase production capacity, and this can be achieved by internal resources, for example overtime, or by external resources, for example subcontracting. In our work, we focus on overtime as a means of flexible production capacity in the multi-item capacitated lot sizing problem with non-identical parallel resources, setup times and costs with allowing backlogging. We are situated in the context of products demands that may exceed the production capacity of the resources at regular time, to satisfy these demands we can resort to overtime at a period or make the choice to realize inventory in previous periods, in the extreme case quantities can be backlogged. We note that the Capacitated Lot Sizing Problem (CLSP) belong to the class of NP-hard combinatorial optimization problems, so the problem considered in this paper is also NP-hard and a metaheuristic can be needed to solve the problem for medium and large size instances. (Diaby et al., 1992a) and (Diaby et al., 1992b), when considering overtime in the CLSP, they have used Lagrangian

relaxation with subgradient optimization, (Diaby et al., 1992a) used the method in a heuristic framework and (Diaby et al., 1992b) within the framework of a branch-and-bound scheme. (Duygu et al., 2019) also considered overtime in the CLSP with stochastic setup times, they had modelled the problem as a two-stage stochastic programming problem and had proposed two heuristics, the first one based on changing the capacity in the deterministic counterpart, and the second one artificially modifies the setup time. (Hindi et al., 2003) also used Lagrangian relaxation with subgradient optimization to solve the CLSP with setup times and overtime, but combined with a smoothing heuristic and local search. (Özdamar and Bozyel, 2000) proposed three heuristic approaches to solve the family lot sizing problem with setup time and overtime decisions, the hierarchical production planning approach, the Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Simulated Annealing algorithm, in their computational experiments they demonstrated that the SA algorithm outperforms the two other approaches and is more efficient. To our knowledge, few researchers consider backlogging in addition to overtime in the CLSP, in the literature we have found the works of (Mohammad and Abdel-Aal, 2019) and (Talita et al, 2022), in this last one, they applied a hybrid exact method combining the Branch and Bound algorithm with Local Search (LS) procedures using a sequential framework in which they used strategies of the Fix and Optimize heuristic and Variable Neighborhood Descent principles.

In this paper we consider simultaneously the backlogging with the overtime decisions in the multi-period multi-product CLSP with non-identical parallel resources and setup times and costs. In section two we introduce a new formulation for the studied problem and in section three we propose a Simulated Annealing algorithm to solve the problem. In section four, we apply the proposed algorithm on a numerical application and compare the results with the CPLEX solver. Finally, conclusions and directions for future works are presented.

2 MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

2.1 Problem description

in this section we describe the multi-item multi-period capacitated lot sizing problem with unrelated parallel resources, setup times and overtime with backlogging allowed, in order to give a mathematical formulation. We consider n product-types that can be produced on m non-identical parallel machines over t periods constituting the planning horizon. Each machine has a limited capacity

CAP_{mp} in time unit per period at regular time. Also, each machine has a production rate per product-type, therefore, each item has a unit production time per machine $Prod_T_{im}$ and a unit production cost per machine and per period $Prod_C_{imp}$. A setup cost $Setup_C_i$ is incurred if a setup is carried out to initiate the production of an item at regular mode, consuming by the way a setup time $Setup_T_i$. Since the production capacity is limited, when the demand exceeds the production capacity of the system at a period, overtime can be needed. However, the capacity at overtime is limited $OCAP_{mp}$ and the production and the setup are more costly ($OProd_C_{imp}$, $OSetup_C_i$). If even the production capacity at overtime is insufficient to fulfil the demand at a period, the exceed demand will be backlogged generating a backlog cost BL_C_i .

2.2 Notation

The notations used in the model are defined as follows:

Sets and indices

- I Set of items, $i \in I = \{1, \dots, n\}$
- M Set of machines, $m \in M = \{1, \dots, k\}$
- P Set of periods, $p \in P = \{1, \dots, t\}$

Parameters

- $Prod_C_{imp}$ Unit production cost of item 'i' in machine 'm' in regular time at period 'p'
- $Hold_i$ Unit holding cost of item 'i'
- $Setup_C_i$ Setup cost of item 'i' in regular time
- $Demand_{ip}$ Demand of item 'i' in period 'p'
- $Setup_T_i$ Setup time of item 'i'
- $Prod_T_{im}$ Unit production time of item 'i' in machine 'm'
- CAP_{mp} Regular time capacity per machine and per period
- BL_C_i Unit backlogging cost of item 'i'
- $OProd_C_{imp}$ Unit production cost of item 'i' on machine 'm' in overtime at period 'p'
- $OSetup_C_i$ Setup cost of item 'i' at overtime
- $OCAP_{mp}$ Overtime capacity in time unit per machine and per period

Decision variables

- Q_{imp} Units of item 'i' produced in machine 'm' in regular time at period 'p'
- x_{imp} A binary variable that takes 1 if there is a

- setup of item ‘i’ in machine ‘m’ in regular time at period ‘p’, else 0
- s_{ip} Inventory level of item ‘i’ at the end of period ‘p’
- bl_{ip} Total accumulated backlog of item ‘i’ at the end of period ‘p’
- OQ_{imp} Units of item ‘i’ produced in machine ‘m’ in overtime at period ‘p’
- or_{imp} A binary variable that takes 1 if item ‘i’ is produced in machine ‘m’ in overtime at period ‘p’, else 0
- ox_{imp} A binary variable that takes 1 if there is a setup of item ‘i’ in machine ‘m’ in overtime at period ‘p’, else 0

x_{imp} , or_{imp} and ox_{imp} are binary variables. Q_{imp} , s_{ip} , bl_{ip} and OQ_{imp} are positive integer variables.

2.3 Assumptions

- We assume that the storage capacity is infinite,
- We assume that the capacity of each machine is constrained,
- We assume that the initial inventory and backlog quantities are zero,
- We assume that the setup is sequence-independent,
- We assume that the demands that can’t be satisfied at a period with regular capacity and overtime capacity are backlogged.

2.4 Model construction

A mixed integer linear programming model for the capacitated lot sizing problem with backlogging and overtime can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Min} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{p=1}^P \text{Prod_C}_{imp} Q_{imp} \\
 & + \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{p=1}^P \text{Setup_C}_i x_{imp} \\
 & + \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{p=1}^P \text{Hold}_i s_{ip} \\
 & + \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{p=1}^P \text{BL_C}_i bl_{ip} \\
 & + \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{p=1}^P \text{OProd_C}_{imp} OQ_{imp} \\
 & + \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{p=1}^P \text{OSetup_C}_i ox_{imp}
 \end{aligned}$$

Subject to:

$$s_{ip} - bl_{ip} = s_{ip-1} - bl_{ip-1} \quad \forall i, p \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \sum_{m=1}^M Q_{imp} \\
 & + \sum_{m=1}^M OQ_{imp} \\
 & - \text{Demand}_{ip} \quad \forall i \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 s_{i1} - bl_{i1} = & \sum_{m=1}^M Q_{im1} \\
 & + \sum_{m=1}^M OQ_{im1} \\
 & - \text{Demand}_{i1} \quad \forall m, p \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{i=1}^I Q_{imp} \text{Prod_T}_{im} \\
 & + \sum_{i=1}^I x_{imp} \text{Setup_T}_i \leq \text{CAP}_{mp} \quad \forall m, p \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{i=1}^I OQ_{imp} \text{Prod_T}_{im} \\
 & + \sum_{i=1}^I ox_{imp} \text{Setup_T}_i \\
 & \leq \text{OCAP}_{mp} \quad \forall i \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{m=1}^M Q_{imp} + \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{m=1}^M OQ_{imp} \\
 + \sum_{p=1}^P bl_{ip} \\
 \geq \sum_{p=1}^P \text{Demand}_{ip} \quad \forall i, m, p \quad (6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$Q_{imp} \leq x_{imp} \sum_{p=1}^P \text{Demand}_{ip} \quad \forall i, m, p \quad (7)$$

$$OQ_{imp} \leq or_{imp} \sum_{p=1}^P \text{Demand}_{ip} \quad \forall i, m, p \quad (7)$$

$$or_{imp} - x_{imp} \leq ox_{imp} \quad \forall m, p > 1 \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^I or_{imp} \leq 1 \quad \forall m, p \quad (9)$$

$$Q_{imp}, OQ_{imp} \geq 0 \quad \forall i, m, p \quad (10)$$

$$bl_{ip}, s_{ip} \geq 0 \quad \forall i, p \quad (11)$$

$$x_{imp}, ox_{imp}, or_{imp} \in \{0,1\} \quad \forall i, m, p \quad (12)$$

The objective function minimizes the total production costs at both regular time and overtime, it includes the manufacturing costs at regular time and overtime, the setup costs at regular time and overtime, the inventory holding costs and the backloging cost. Equations (1) and (2) are material balance constraints. Equations (3) and (4) are production capacity constraints at regular time and over time respectively. Equation (5) represents the demand satisfaction constraint, if a demand of a product type cannot be satisfied by the manufacturing at regular time and overtime of period p , it is backloged to later periods and a backloging cost is generated at period p . Equations (6), (7) and (8) express the link between decision variables at regular time and overtime. A product type can be produced at a machine m at regular time of period p if there was a setup for, the same for the overtime but only if the product type was not setup at regular time. Equation (9) ensures that only one product type can be produced by period and by machine at overtime. Equations (10), (11) and (12) are about the definition of the variables.

3 SIMULATED ANNEALING ALGORITHM

In this section, we use the SA as a metaheuristic algorithm to solve the studied problem. The SA is inspired by thermodynamics and was proposed for the first time in 1983 by Scott Kirkpatrick et al. (Kirkpatrick et al., 1983). It is a local search method based on the neighborhood search concept, where the space of solutions is explored by moving from a solution to the best solution in its neighborhood at each iteration. The algorithm begins as shown in figure 1 with an initial solution y_0 that can be generated randomly and an initial temperature T_0 . At each temperature level and at each iteration, a neighborhood solution y_n is searched and evaluated using the fitness function $f_{(y_n)}$. If this movement improves the current solution, the neighborhood solution will be accepted, otherwise it can be accepted with probability $p = \exp\left(\frac{f_{(y_n)} - f_{(y_i)}}{T_i}\right)$. After a maximum number of iterations or a termination criterion, the temperature is decreased using a cooling rate α . And so on until a final temperature is reached and the best solution of all moves is returned. In the following, we describe the initial solution generation method and neighborhood solution generation method used in the studied lot sizing problem with backloging and overtime.

Fig. 1 Simulated Annealing Algorithm

3.1 Initial solution generation method

The generation of a feasible initial solution consists in establishing a production plan for the manufacture of items on non-identical parallel machines. It defines the quantities to be produced for each item in regular and overtime modes, as well as the quantities to be backloged by period. For each period from the planning horizon, the following steps are repeated:

Step 1.A: maximization of machine capacity utilization in regular mode, until period demands are met or production capacity is saturated.

Step 2.A: if the period's demand is not fully fulfilled, continue to use the machines in overtime mode.

Step 3.A: if, after saturation of the production capacity of the machines in overtime mode, there is still unmet demand, it will be backlogged.

3.2 Neighborhood solution generation method

The outline of the proposed method is as follows:

Step 1.B: Perturbation of the current solution by removing the production of an item from a machine chosen randomly in regular mode of a period also chosen randomly, then elimination of backlog and overtime quantities of all periods.

For each period p of the planning horizon, repeat the following steps:

Step 2.B: verification of demand satisfaction for each item

Step 3.B: use of production capacity of machines in regular mode of period p to satisfy demand

Step 4.B: if the demand of period p is not yet fulfilled and the production capacity of the machines in regular mode of period p is saturated, use the production capacities in regular mode of the periods preceding period p .

Step 5.B: if after saturation of the production capacity of the machines in regular mode for all periods of the planning horizon up to period p , the demand for this period is not yet met, use the production capacity in overtime mode of period p .

Step 6.B: At this stage, once the production capacities of the machines in regular mode of all periods up to period p and in overtime mode of period p are saturated, if any demand remains unsatisfied, it will be backlogged.

4 COMPUTATIONAL RESULTS

As mentioned in section one, in this work we consider the problem of lot sizing with non-identical parallel resources, setups, backlogs and overtime. To solve this problem, we first implemented the proposed mathematical model on the solver CPLEX Studio IDE 22.1.1. Then, we coded the SA algorithm in java programming language. Several experimentations have been done with CPLEX and the SA method. In this section, we illustrate the functioning of the initial solution generation method and the neighborhood solution generation method of the SA algorithm through example 1. After that, we present a second example that compares the solution obtained by CPLEX with the one obtained by the SA algorithm.

For the first example we consider 2 machines (m_1, m_2) to manufacture two products (i_1, i_2) over two periods (p_1, p_2) where $CAP_{mp} = 8$ time units and $OCAP_{mp} = 4$ time units. The demands are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Demands for the example

	Period 1	Period 2
Item 1	10	25
Item 2	10	40

When constructing an initial solution, the quantities to be manufactured for each item and on each machine are randomly generated. The process is designed to allocate demand, item by item and machine by machine, starting with regular mode, then overtime mode and finally backlogging. Table 2 details how the method works and the results obtained. Inventory and backlog quantities are shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Sequences of the functioning of the initial solution generation method

Seq.	Period	Mode	Items	Quantities		Remaining unfulfilled demand by period	Remaining capacity
				m_1	m_2		
1	1	Regular time	i_1	10		0	5.2
2			i_2	7		3	0.4
3			i_2		3		0
4	2	Regular time	i_1	25		0	3.25
5			i_2	3		37	0.34
6			i_2		13		24
7		Overtime	i_2	8		16	0.24
8			i_2		8		8

Table 3. Inventory and backlog quantities of the initial solution

	Inventory		Backlog quantities	
	p_1	p_2	p_1	p_2
i_1	0	0	0	0
i_2	0	0	0	8

From the obtained initial solution, we generate a neighborhood solution and the main sequences of the method are presented in the tables 4-6. Table 4 reproduce the plan found with the initial solution generation method for example 1. The quantities in bold are the quantities to be deleted (which results in 7 units of item 2 as unsatisfied demand in period 1 and 21 units in period 2 of the same item). Table 5

gives the production plan of the new solution after meeting the demand at the first period. The grayed-out values are the modified values from the previous plan. The 7 units of item 2 deleted have been added to machine 2. Table 6 represents the final plan of the new solution obtained after realizing the changes for the reassignment of the unsatisfied demand of the second period, from 21 units of item 2 removed, 7 units have been reassigned to the first period on machine 1. The remaining 14 units have been produced in overtime of period 2, 8 units in machine 1 and 6 units in machine 2.

Table 4. The production plan of the initial solution and the quantities to be removed as in the first step of the method

Regular mode	Period 1			Period 2		
	Quantities		Remaining capacity	Quantities		Remaining capacity
	i_1	i_2		i_1	i_2	
m_1	10	7	0.4	25	3	0.34
m_2		3	5		13	0
Overtime mode	Period 1			Period 2		
	Quantities		Remaining capacity	Quantities		Remaining capacity
	i_1	i_2		i_1	i_2	
m_1			2	8	0.24	
m_2			2	8	0	
Remaining unfulfilled demand	0	0		0	8	
Inventory	0	0		0	0	

Table 5. The production plan of the neighborhood solution including the changes made to meet the demand in period 1

Regular mode	Period 1			Period 2		
	Quantities		Remaining capacity	Quantities		Remaining capacity
	i_1	i_2		i_1	i_2	
m_1	10		5.2	25	3	0.34
m_2		10	1.5		13	0
Overtime mode	Period 1			Period 2		
	Quantities		Remaining capacity	Quantities		Remaining capacity
	i_1	i_2		i_1	i_2	
m_1			2		4	
m_2			2		4	
Remaining unfulfilled demand	0	0		0	24	
Inventory	0	0		0	0	

Table 6. The final production plan of the neighborhood solution including the changes made to meet the demand in period 2

Regular mode	Period 1			Period 2		
	Quantities		Remaining capacity	Quantities		Remaining capacity
	i_1	i_2		i_1	i_2	
m_1	10	7	0.4	25	3	0.34

m_2		13	0		13	0
Overtime mode	Period 1			Period 2		
	Quantities		Remaining capacity	Quantities		Remaining capacity
	i_1	i_2		i_1	i_2	
m_1			2		8	0.24
m_2			2		6	1
Remaining unfulfilled demand	0	0		0	0	
Inventory	0	0		0	0	

For the second example, we consider 3 products (i_1, i_2, i_3) to be produced over 3 periods (p_1, p_2, p_3) on 2 machines (m_1, m_3) to satisfy the following demands (10, 10, 10) for i_1 , (10,10,20) for i_2 and (10,10,15) for i_3 . In table 7, we give the production plan obtained after solving the mathematical model on CPLEX solver. Table 8 presents the solution generated by the SA algorithm. The gap between the objective functions of the two solutions was of the order of 3%.

Table 7. The solution obtained by CPLEX solver for example 2

Regular mode		Quantities								
		Period 1			Period 2			Period 3		
		i_1	i_2	i_3	i_1	i_2	i_3	i_1	i_2	i_3
	m_1		12		20		1		13	
m_2	10		2		8	1			1	
Overtime mode		Quantities								
		Period 1			Period 2			Period 3		
		i_1	i_2	i_3	i_1	i_2	i_3	i_1	i_2	i_3
	m_1			2			4		7	
m_2			5			5			5	
Inventory		2		10						
Backlogs			1							9

Table 8. The solution obtained by the SA algorithm for example 2

Regular mode		Quantities								
		Period 1			Period 2			Period 3		
		i_1	i_2	i_3	i_1	i_2	i_3	i_1	i_2	i_3
	m_1		10		10	10		10	7	
m_2	10		3			3			13	
Overtime mode		Quantities								
		Period 1			Period 2			Period 3		
		i_1	i_2	i_3	i_1	i_2	i_3	i_1	i_2	i_3
	m_1			4			4			2
m_2			3			3			3	
Inventory										
Backlogs										10

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we addressed the multi-product multi-period capacitated lot sizing problem with setups and overtime with backlogging allowed. A new mathematical model was introduced, tested and resolved using two different approaches: an exact approach using the CPLEX solver and in the second approach we used a metaheuristic more precisely the SA in order to solve the problem for medium and large size instances.

The numerical results obtained from the experimentations carried out have enabled us to propose an optimal plan for the allocation of machines and an optimal assignment of the different modes taking into account the demand which varies from one period to another and from one customer to another.

According to the results obtained, the gap between the approximate and exact methods is of the order of 0.06% for small instances, which shows that the metaheuristic method is converging. And by increasing the parameters in the system (number of products, number of periods, number of machines) the gap is of the order of 3%, which remains acceptable for the studied problem.

This study has helped to guide decision-makers in their choice of the various modes used (regular mode, overtime mode) in order to maximize their profits while satisfying customers and minimizing their costs.

As for future research directions, we envisage to reduce the gap by trying other metaheuristics such as the Genetic Algorithm or hybrid heuristics.

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